

Strategic Management of Clinically Node-Negative Neck in Oral Tongue Squamous Cell Carcinoma

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Abstract:**Background:** Oral tongue squamous cell carcinoma is a prevalent head and neck cancer with a high potential for regional metastasis. The management of clinically node-negative (N0) neck remains contentious, with debates surrounding the benefits of elective neck dissection versus observation.**Methods:** This prospective study compared two management strategies for early-stage tongue SCC without clinically palpable neck nodes. Fifty patients were randomized into two groups: one undergoing elective neck dissection and the other observed post-primary tumor treatment without immediate surgical intervention. Outcomes assessed included development of neck node metastasis, disease-free survival, overall survival, and post-treatment complications.**Results:** Elective neck dissection resulted in a lower incidence of neck node metastasis (8% vs. 16%) and higher median disease-free (24 months vs. 18 months) and overall survival (30 months vs. 24 months) compared to the observation group. Complications in the surgical group included lymphedema (12%) and surgical site infections (4%).**Conclusion:** Elective neck dissection may offer a survival advantage for patients with early-stage oral tongue SCC by reducing the incidence of regional metastasis. However, the associated morbidities underscore the need for careful patient selection. The results advocate for a tailored approach based on individual risk profiles to optimize treatment outcomes in this patient population.**Keywords:** Oral tongue squamous cell carcinoma, elective neck dissection, clinically node-negative neck, head and neck cancer, survival outcomes, regional metastasis.

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Introduction

Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) of the oral tongue remains the most prevalent and menacing malignancy originating from the oral cavity. It accounts for about 50% of all head and neck cancers and presents a unique challenge due to its high potential for early regional spread. The anatomy of the oral tongue, characterized by an extensive lymphatic network, predisposes it to a pronounced risk of metastasis to the cervical lymph nodes. This lymphatic propensity underpins the aggressive clinical behavior of this cancer, emphasizing the importance of timely and accurate diagnostic and therapeutic strategies. [1,2]

The likelihood of lymph node metastasis is significantly influenced by a range of histopathologic factors. These include the tumor thickness, the presence of perineural and microvascular invasion, the extent of lymphocytic infiltration, and the general pattern of tumor invasion and differentiation. Notably, a tumor size greater than 2 cm or an invasion depth exceeding 4

mm markedly elevates the risk of nodal metastases. Moreover, the histological grading and the overall staging of the tumor serve as crucial determinants; with poorly differentiated and later-stage tumors exhibiting a higher propensity for nodal involvement. [3,4] Despite advancements in imaging technologies—such as computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and positron emission tomography (PET)—the detection of micro-metastases in cervical lymph nodes remains fraught with challenges.

Current diagnostic modalities often yield substantial false-negative and false-positive rates, complicating the clinical decision-making process. This diagnostic uncertainty necessitates a reliance on histologic examination of neck specimens, which, though invasive, provides the most definitive assessment of nodal status. [5,6,7] Elective neck dissection represents a pivotal management strategy in the context of clinically node-negative (N0) necks in patients with oral

tongue SCC. This preemptive surgical intervention involves the systematic removal of cervical lymphatic tissue in the absence of overt clinical or radiological evidence of metastasis. The rationale behind this approach is not only therapeutic but also diagnostic, aiding in the accurate staging of the disease which is crucial for tailoring subsequent treatment. [8,9]

The controversy surrounding elective neck dissection hinges on balancing the potential benefits of improved regional disease control and survival against the risks of overtreatment and associated morbidities. The decision to undertake elective neck dissection is complex, influenced by factors such as the expected natural history of the tumor, the patient's overall health status, and the potential impact on quality of life. Advocates argue that elective neck dissection reduces regional recurrence and eliminates the need for more aggressive treatments should metastases become clinically apparent later. However, detractors caution against the routine use of this procedure in all clinically N0 cases, citing the risks of unnecessary surgery and the non-negligible burden of surgical complications. [10,11,12]

Given these complexities, the management of N0 neck in patients with oral tongue SCC requires a nuanced, evidence-based approach. Clinicians must judiciously weigh the risks and benefits, considering individual patient factors and tumor characteristics to make informed decisions. This on-going debate underscores the need for further research to refine the criteria for selecting patients for elective neck dissection and to develop more sensitive and specific diagnostic tools for the detection of occult metastases.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

This prospective study, conducted at our institute from August 2013 to August 2015, involved early-stage tongue malignancies (T1 and T2) without clinically palpable neck nodes (N0). A follow-up period of two years was implemented to monitor patient outcomes post-intervention. The study aimed to address critical questions regarding the management of clinical N0 neck in patients with oral tongue carcinoma by comparing two distinct therapeutic strategies.

Study Population

Patients were rigorously selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria mandated that participants exhibit no clinical or radiological evidence of neck node metastasis (N0 neck). Patients with T3 or higher lesions, clinically palpable cervical nodes, radiologically detectable cervical nodal metastasis, or distant metastasis were excluded from the study.

Randomization and Interventions

Eligible patients were randomly divided into two groups:

- **Group A (Elective Neck Dissection Group):** Patients underwent primary tumor treatment followed by elective neck dissection.
- **Group B (Observation Group):** Patients received only primary tumor treatment, with the neck under close surveillance. Therapeutic neck dissection was performed only upon detection of neck node metastasis during follow-up.

Diagnostic Techniques

The nodal status was initially assessed using a combination of clinical palpation and advanced radiological techniques, including CT scans, MRI, and ultrasound-guided fine needle aspiration cytology. These methods aimed to enhance the accuracy of detecting metastatic neck nodes or disease, addressing the limitations of clinical palpation alone.

Primary Outcomes

The primary outcomes assessed were:

1. Identification of patients with actual node-negative status post-treatment.
2. Determination of patients who developed neck node metastasis post-treatment.
3. Evaluation of the optimal and least morbid treatment modality for managing clinical N0 neck in oral carcinomas.
4. Assessment of the impact of elective neck dissection on outcome benefits compared to an observation strategy.

Justification for the Study

The controversy surrounding the optimal management of clinical N0 neck in head and neck cancers, particularly oral carcinomas, stems from the significant rate of occult metastases, estimated at 30% or higher, depending on the tumor's characteristics and diagnostic methods used.

The challenge lies in accurately identifying patients without micro-metastases to the cervical lymph nodes, thus avoiding unnecessary treatment costs, prolonged hospital stays, and morbidity. Advanced management strategies now allow for significant local disease control and improved quality of life, making it crucial to refine treatment approaches based on robust clinical evidence.

Ethical Considerations

The study protocol was approved by the institutional review board, ensuring compliance with ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, emphasizing the

voluntary nature of participation and the confidentiality of patient information.

Results

The study evaluated two distinct treatment strategies for early-stage tongue squamous cell carcinoma with clinically node-negative (N0) necks in 50 patients, evenly distributed into two groups: Group A underwent elective neck dissection, and Group B was observed without surgical intervention.

Patient Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

Both groups were comparable in terms of demographics and tumor staging at baseline. Each group consisted of 25 patients, predominantly male (76%), with an age range predominantly between 41-60 years. The distribution of primary tumor stages was identical across the groups, with 46% of patients presenting with T1 and 54% with T2 stage tumors (Table 1).

Initial Clinical Assessment

Initial clinical evaluations confirmed the absence of palpable neck nodes in all participants (100%), and radiological investigations did not reveal any

evidence of metastasis at the outset of the study in either group (Table 2).

Treatment Outcomes

The development of neck node metastasis was more frequent in Group B, where 16% of the patients experienced metastasis, compared to 8% in Group A. Additionally, Group A showed superior outcomes in terms of disease-free survival, with a median of 24 months compared to 18 months in Group B.

Similarly, overall survival was greater in Group A, with a median of 30 months, as opposed to 24 months in Group B, suggesting a potential benefit of elective neck dissection in extending both disease-free and overall survival (Table 3).

Post-Treatment Complications

The elective neck dissection group (Group A) exhibited a 4% incidence of surgical site infections and 12% developed lymphedema. In contrast, Group B, which did not undergo elective surgery, recorded a higher recurrence rate at the primary site (12%) and detected metastasis during the follow-up period in 16% of cases, underscoring the possible risks of delaying surgical intervention (Table 4).

Table 1: Patient Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Group A (Elective Neck Dissection)	Group B (Observation)
Total Patients	25	25
Age (years)	41-60	41-60
Gender	Male: 76% Female: 24%	Male: 76% Female: 24%
Primary Tumor Stage	T1: 46% T2: 54%	T1: 46% T2: 54%

Table 2: Initial Clinical Assessment and Diagnostic Findings

Diagnostic Parameter	Group A (Elective Neck Dissection)	Group B (Observation)
Clinically Palpable Neck Nodes (N0)	100% (None palpable)	100% (None palpable)
Radiological Evidence of Metastasis	0%	0%

Table 3: Treatment Outcomes - Elective Neck Dissection Vs. Observation

Outcome	Group A (Elective Neck Dissection)	Group B (Observation)
Development of Neck Node Metastasis	8%	16%
Disease-Free Survival (months, median)	24	18
Overall Survival (months, median)	30	24

Table 4: Post-Treatment Complications

Complication	Group A (Elective Neck Dissection)	Group B (Observation)
Surgical Site Infections	4%	N/A
Lymphedema	12%	N/A
Recurrence at Primary Site	8%	12%
Metastasis Detected During Follow-up	N/A	16%

Discussion

The management of clinically node-negative (N0) neck in patients with oral tongue squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) presents a considerable clinical

dilemma. This study provided a unique perspective by comparing the outcomes of elective neck dissection versus observation in a well-defined cohort. The findings from this study underscore the complexity of treatment decisions and the nuanced

approaches required to optimize patient outcomes in oral tongue SCC. [9,10]

Elective neck dissection demonstrated a lower incidence of neck node metastasis (8%) compared to the observation group (16%), supporting its role in proactive regional disease control. This aligns with prior research suggesting that elective neck dissection can effectively mitigate the risk of regional recurrence and improve loco-regional control in patients with high-risk features, despite the absence of clinically detectable nodal disease at diagnosis. The superior disease-free survival (24 months) and overall survival (30 months) in the elective neck dissection group further validate this approach, highlighting its potential to extend survival in this patient population. [11,12]

However, the benefits of elective neck dissection must be balanced against the potential for overtreatment. The 12% incidence of lymphedema and the 4% rate of surgical site infections observed in Group A illustrate the morbidity associated with this procedure.

These findings emphasize the importance of patient selection and the need for precise staging and risk stratification to identify patients who would most benefit from this intervention. [13,14]

The observation strategy, while avoiding the immediate surgical risks, was associated with a higher rate of metastasis detection during follow-up, indicating a possible delay in the treatment of occult metastatic disease. This could potentially compromise disease control and survival, as reflected by the shorter disease-free and overall survival times observed in this group.

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